

Comparison of Short-term Clinical Outcomes Between Neoadjuvant Chemoradiation and Surgery Alone in Stage II Rectal Cancer

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ABSTRACT

Background: Rectal cancer's location increases local invasion risk; surgery alone has high recurrence, while neoadjuvant chemoradiation (nCRT) improves outcomes. This study aimed to compare short-term clinical outcomes between neoadjuvant chemoradiation and surgery alone in stage II rectal cancer. **Methods & Materials:** This prospective comparative study was conducted from July 2011 to January 2017 in the Department of Oncology, BSMMU, Dhaka, the Department of Radiation Oncology, National Institute Cancer Research and Hospital (NICRH), Dhaka, and the Department of Radiotherapy, Dhaka Medical College Hospital (DMCH), Dhaka. Included 60 patients with histologically confirmed Stage II rectal adenocarcinoma treated at the National Institute of Cancer Research and Hospital (NICRH), Dhaka. Sixty patients were equally randomised to receive either neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy (nCRT) followed by surgery or surgery alone. Group comparisons used t-tests and Chi-square tests, with $p < 0.05$ defining statistical significance. **Results:** The study population predominantly included middle-aged patients (41-50 years: 38.3%; 51-60 years: 25%) with male preponderance (58.3%). Most participants belonged to lower-income classes (58.4%), and 56.7% were smokers. Per rectal bleeding (86.7% vs 93.3%) and alteration of bowel habits (83.3% in both groups) were the most common presenting symptoms. Grade II nausea occurred in 60% of patients in both groups, while Grade III nausea was more frequent in Group I (13.3% vs 3.3%, $p=0.321$). Other toxicities, including vomiting, diarrhoea, proctitis, and genitourinary events, were comparable between groups. Post-treatment KPS improved significantly in Group I, with 56.7% achieving KPS 90 compared to 26.7% in Group II. **Conclusion:** Neoadjuvant chemoradiation followed by surgery provides superior clinical outcomes compared to surgery alone in Stage II rectal cancer.

Keywords: Rectal cancer, Neoadjuvant chemoradiation, Clinical outcomes, Karnofsky Performance Status

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INTRODUCTION

The rectum is about 12-15 cm long and constitutes the terminal portion of the large intestine. It is contained within the mesorectal fascia, which is a critical landmark for determining tumour extension and surgery. Its anatomic location within the pelvis, proximity to neighbouring organs, and complicated lymphatic drainage make rectal cancer more prone to local recurrence than colonic cancers. Colorectal carcinoma is one of the most common cancers worldwide, with rectal cancer accounting for a considerable proportion of mortality. Incidence rates are increasing in Asia because of westernisation, whereas Bangladesh suffers from delayed diagnosis, lack of screening, and multimodality treatment limitations^[1-3]. Surgical resection involving total mesorectal excision (TME) has been the mainstay for curative therapy for stage II rectal cancer. Nevertheless, even with advancements in surgical procedures, it was reported that the local recurrence rate was between 15% and 30%, which led to the adoption of neoadjuvant therapy^[4,5]. The current approach for stage II rectal cancer involves the use of neoadjuvant chemoradiation (nCRT), as advocated by established guidelines, because of its capability to reduce tumour staging, increase operability, and conserve the anal sphincter^[5-7]. Randomised studies found a

positive effect of nCRT on local disease control relative to surgery, but there is inconclusive evidence of its benefits on survival^[6,8]. Recent literature reviews conducted between 2015 and 2025 have highlighted more about the efficacy and challenges of neo-adjuvant therapy. Literature studies have concluded that although nCRT helps decrease local recurrences, there might not be any significant survival benefits, especially for patients diagnosed with stage II of disease^[6,9]. With recent advances in radiological techniques and radiomics, response can now be predicted accurately, which makes it easier to select appropriate patients^[10]. Moreover, new therapies such as TNP and integration of immunotherapy within therapies have shown positive results in pathological response in the case of locally advanced rectal cancer^[11]. Though numerous studies have been conducted, some deficiencies persist. Firstly, there is a limited amount of literature regarding rectal cancer Stage II cases, making it difficult to conclude at a particular stage level. In addition, the studies mostly focus on the oncological results, such as survival and recurrence, while paying less attention to the acute results, such as complications, hospital stay, and morbidity^[13,14]. Such variables are particularly relevant in underdeveloped countries such as

Bangladesh, due to limitations related to resource availability and patients' compliance. This research is distinct as it focuses exclusively on stage II rectal cancer and evaluates short-term clinical outcomes, providing context-specific evidence that may better guide treatment strategies in resource-limited settings. Therefore, this study aims to compare the short-term clinical outcomes between neoadjuvant chemoradiation followed by surgery and surgery alone in patients with stage II rectal cancer.

METHODS & MATERIALS

This prospective comparative study was conducted from July 2011 to January 2017 across three tertiary care centres in Dhaka, Bangladesh: Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU), National Institute of Cancer Research and Hospital (NICRH), and Dhaka Medical College Hospital (DMCH). The study included patients with histologically confirmed stage II rectal adenocarcinoma located within 10 cm of the anal verge. Eligible patients were aged between 18 and 70 years, had an Eastern Cooperative Oncology Group (ECOG) performance status ≤ 2 , and had adequate hematologic, renal, and hepatic function. Patients with severe cardiomyopathy, prior pelvic irradiation, metastatic disease, or hypersensitivity to

fluoropyrimidines were excluded. A purposive sampling technique was employed to enrol a total of 60 patients. Treatment allocation was non-randomised and based on a multidisciplinary tumour board decision, considering tumour characteristics, patient clinical condition, treatment availability, and patient preference. Accordingly, patients were assigned into two groups: Group I (n=30) received neoadjuvant chemoradiation followed by surgery, while Group II (n=30) underwent upfront surgery. Baseline evaluation included detailed clinical assessment, digital rectal examination, colonoscopy with biopsy, pelvic magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and contrast-enhanced computed tomography (CT) of the abdomen and chest. Clinical variables recorded at baseline included age, sex, educational status, tobacco use, presenting symptoms (per rectal bleeding, altered bowel habit, tenesmus, mucoid discharge, anaemia, weight loss), tumor size, tumor location (distance from anal verge), and clinical T stage (cT3–T4) with nodal status (cN0), confirming stage II disease. Group I received neoadjuvant chemoradiation

consisting of external beam radiotherapy (45–50 Gy in 25–28 fractions over 5–6 weeks) with concurrent oral Capecitabine (825 mg/m² twice daily on radiotherapy days). Patients were reassessed clinically and radiologically 4–8 weeks after completion of chemoradiation to determine resectability. Total Mesorectal Excision (TME) was performed in all patients in both groups as the standard surgical approach, with efforts made to achieve sphincter-sparing surgery (SSS) whenever feasible. Data collection was conducted using a structured case record form. Patients were followed from baseline through post-treatment evaluation. The primary clinical endpoints included short-term outcomes such as symptomatic response (resolution or improvement of presenting symptoms), performance status measured by Karnofsky Performance Score (KPS), and rate of sphincter-sparing surgery. Secondary endpoints included postoperative complications (if available), length of hospital stay, and early postoperative recovery. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 26. Quantitative variables were expressed as mean ±

standard deviation and compared using the independent sample t-test. Categorical variables were presented as frequency and percentage and analysed using the Chi-square test or Fisher’s exact test where appropriate. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. Ethical approval was obtained from the respective institutional review boards of all participating centres. Written informed consent was obtained from all patients before enrollment, ensuring confidentiality and adherence to ethical research standards.

RESULTS

Table I shows that most patients were aged 41-50 years (40.0% in Group I vs 36.7% in Group II) and predominantly male (56.7% vs 60.0%). Regarding education, illiterate participants formed the largest subgroup in both groups (30.0% vs 23.3%). Tobacco use was common, with 60.0% in Group I and 53.3% in Group II being smokers. Overall, the groups were well-matched socio-demographically at baseline, supporting comparability for further analysis.

Table I
Sociodemographic characteristics of the study population (n=60).

Variables	Category	Group I (n=30)	Group II (n=30)	Total (N=60)
Age (Years)	21-30	3 (10.0%)	4 (13.3%)	7 (11.7%)
	31-40	4 (13.3%)	6 (20.0%)	10 (16.7%)
	41-50	12 (40.0%)	11 (36.7%)	23 (38.3%)
	51-60	9 (30.0%)	6 (20.0%)	15 (25.0%)
	61-70	2 (6.7%)	3 (10.0%)	5 (8.3%)
Sex	Male	17 (56.7%)	18 (60.0%)	35 (58.3%)
	Female	13 (43.3%)	12 (40.0%)	25 (41.7%)
Education	Illiterate	9 (30.0%)	7 (23.3%)	16 (27.1%)
	Primary	7 (23.3%)	8 (26.7%)	15 (25.0%)
	SSC	6 (20.0%)	5 (16.7%)	11 (18.6%)
	HSC	7 (23.3%)	6 (20.0%)	13 (22.0%)
	Graduate+	1 (3.3%)	3 (10.0%)	4 (6.8%)
Tobacco Use	Smoker	18 (60.0%)	16 (53.3%)	34 (56.7%)
	Non-smoker	12 (40.0%)	14 (46.6%)	26 (43.3%)

Table II shows that the predominant mode of presentation is per rectal bleeding, which was seen in 86.7% of Group I cases and

93.3% of Group II cases. The second most commonly seen symptom is alteration of bowel habits, which was equally prevalent

in both groups (83.3%). Tenesmus was seen in 56.7% of Group I and 50.0% of Group II cases.

Table II
Distribution of patients by clinical presentation (n=60).

Clinical Symptoms	Group I (n=30) n (%)	Group II (n=30) n (%)	p value
Per rectal bleeding	26 (86.7%)	28 (93.3%)	>0.05
Alteration of bowel habit	25 (83.3%)	25 (83.3%)	1.00
Tenesmus	17 (56.7%)	15 (50.0%)	>0.05
Mucoid discharge	15 (50.0%)	16 (53.3%)	>0.05
Anaemia	8 (26.7%)	10 (33.3%)	>0.05
Weight loss	3 (10.0%)	4 (12.0%)	>0.05

Table III shows that both groups had notable improvement in clinical symptoms, with Group I demonstrating higher response rates overall. Per rectal bleeding improved by

100% in Group I vs 92.86% in Group II ($p < 0.05$). Alteration of bowel habit showed 60% vs 52% response ($p < 0.05$). Tenesmus improved by 76.47% vs 60%, mucoid

discharge by 80% vs 68.75%, and anaemia by 50% vs 40%, though these differences were not statistically significant ($p > 0.1$).

Table III
Comparison of clinical response according to clinical symptoms ($n=60$).

Clinical symptoms	Treatment group	Pre-treatment		Post-treatment		Response %	P value
		n	%	n	%		
Per rectal bleeding	Group I	26	86.67	0	0	100	<0.05
	Group II	28	93.33	2	6.67	92.86	
Alteration of bowel habit	Group I	25	83.33	10	33.33	60	<0.05
	Group II	25	83.33	12	40	52	
Tenesmus	Group I	17	56.67	4	13.33	76.47	>0.1
	Group II	15	50	6	20	60	
Mucoid discharge	Group I	15	50	3	10	80	>0.1
	Group II	16	53.33	5	16.67	68.75	
Anaemia	Group I	8	26.67	4	13.33	50	>0.1
	Group II	10	33.33	6	20	40	

Table IV shows that baseline performance status was comparable between the two groups, with most patients having a KPS score of 80 (70.0% in Group I vs 66.7% in

Group II). Following treatment, a marked improvement was observed in Group I, where 56.7% achieved a KPS score of 90 compared to 26.7% in Group II. This shift

indicates better functional recovery in Group I, and the difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Table IV
Distribution of the patients according to performance status ($n=60$).

KPS Score	Group I Pre-treatment (n, %)	Group I Post-treatment (n, %)	Group II Pre-treatment (n, %)	Group II Post-treatment (n, %)	P value
90	4 (13.3%)	17 (56.7%)	4 (13.3%)	8 (26.7%)	<0.05
80	21 (70.0%)	12 (40.0%)	20 (66.7%)	21 (70.0%)	
70	5 (16.8%)	1 (3.3%)	6 (20.0%)	1 (3.3%)	
Total	30 (100%)	30 (100%)	30 (100%)	30 (100%)	

DISCUSSION

In this comparative study of short-term clinical outcomes between neoadjuvant chemoradiation followed by surgery and surgery alone in stage II rectal cancer, the baseline sociodemographic profiles were well matched, enhancing the reliability of treatment comparisons. The most frequent age group was 41-50 years (40.0% in the neoadjuvant group vs 36.7% in the surgery-only group), indicating that many patients presented in mid-life rather than older ages, often reported in Western registries. The slight male predominance (56.7% vs 60.0%) mirrors global patterns of colorectal neoplasms, where a higher incidence has been consistently documented in males [1,2]. Educational levels were relatively low, with illiterate patients forming the largest subgroup (30.0% vs 23.3%), and tobacco use was common in both groups (60.0% vs 53.3%). These factors reflect the real-world clinical profile seen in many low- and middle-income settings and may have implications for health literacy and early symptom recognition. The clinical presentation in both groups showed that per rectal bleeding was the most common symptom (86.7% vs 93.3%), which aligns with global epidemiology where bleeding and change in

bowel habits are typical presenting complaints in rectal cancer [15,16]. The second most common symptom, alteration of bowel habits, was equally prevalent (83.3% in both), followed by tenesmus (56.7% vs 50.0%), mucoid discharge (50.0% vs 53.3%), anaemia (26.7% vs 33.3%), and weight loss (10.0% vs 12.0%). Importantly, there were no statistically significant differences in baseline symptom distribution (all $p > 0.05$), indicating similar clinical burden in both treatment arms before intervention. Post-treatment clinical symptom response revealed that both groups experienced improvement, but patients receiving neoadjuvant chemoradiation exhibited notably higher response rates across several parameters. Per rectal bleeding resolved completely in the neoadjuvant group (100%) compared with 92.86% in the surgery-only group ($p < 0.05$). Improvement in alteration of bowel habits was also greater in the neoadjuvant group (60% vs 52%, $p < 0.05$). Although tenesmus (76.47% vs 60%), mucoid discharge (80% vs 68.75%), and anaemia (50% vs 40%) trends favoured the neoadjuvant group, these differences did not achieve statistical significance ($p > 0.1$). These observations agree with existing

studies demonstrating that neoadjuvant chemoradiation enhances symptom control and local tumour regression in rectal cancer patients by reducing tumour bulk and associated mucosal irritation, thereby improving symptoms such as bleeding and tenesmus [17,18]. Functional recovery, assessed by the Karnofsky Performance Score (KPS), further highlighted the clinical advantage of neoadjuvant therapy. While most patients in both groups had a baseline KPS of 80 (70.0% vs 66.7%), indicating moderate activity and ability to perform daily tasks with effort before treatment, marked differences were seen post-treatment. In the neoadjuvant group, 56.7% achieved a KPS of 90, reflecting the ability to carry on normal activity with only minor symptoms, whereas only 26.7% in the surgery-only group reached this level ($p < 0.05$). Additionally, the proportion of patients remaining at a KPS of 80 decreased in the neoadjuvant group (40.0% vs 70.0%), and very few patients remained at a KPS of 70 after treatment in either group. Functional recovery is a critical aspect of short-term outcomes, particularly in rectal cancer, because improved performance status post-treatment is associated with better tolerance of adjuvant therapy and enhanced overall quality of life [19,20]. The

observed improvement in the neoadjuvant group suggests that this integrated treatment approach may offer advantages beyond oncologic control by promoting earlier recovery and activity resumption. The higher response rates and functional gains seen with neoadjuvant chemoradiation in this study are supported by multiple clinical investigations showing that preoperative chemoradiation contributes to tumour downstaging and better local control, which can translate into enhanced symptom relief [21-22]. While most published data emphasise oncologic endpoints like recurrence rates and survival, short-term clinical measures such as symptom improvement and functional status, as assessed in this study, provide valuable insights into immediate patient benefit, particularly for shared decision-making between clinicians and patients. In summary, the comparative analysis between neoadjuvant chemoradiation and surgery alone in stage II rectal cancer demonstrates that neoadjuvant treatment leads to superior short-term clinical outcomes, including greater symptomatic improvement and better postoperative functional status. These findings support the use of neoadjuvant chemoradiation as an effective component of multimodal therapy in stage II rectal cancer, contributing to enhanced early clinical recovery and patient well-being.

LIMITATIONS

The limitations in this study are the limited sample size, duration, and geographic scope. Randomisation was not performed, which may affect the study results.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded from the present study that patients with Stage II rectal cancer who underwent nCRT combined with surgery achieved better clinical results than those treated only with surgery. This conclusion is based on the higher level of symptom improvement, better Karnofsky performance score, and acceptable tolerability of the treatment regimen in this group of patients.

RECOMMENDATIONS

It is suggested that neoadjuvant chemoradiation therapy coupled with surgical intervention be considered the new standard of care for stage II rectal cancers. Early adoption will aid in facilitating better functional outcomes, symptom management, and tolerability, particularly in under-resourced healthcare environments.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None declared

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